

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPLICATIONS AFTER LIVER RESECTIONS- HEMORRHAGE

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Abstract

Liver surgery is historically one of the "youngest" areas in abdominal surgery, but he most technically challenging surgical procedure in due to the complex anatomical arrangement in the liver.

The development of liver resection surgery is associated with the improvement of parenchymal dissection techniques and reliable hemostasis and biliostasis

The International Study Group of Liver Surgery (ISGLS) provides definitions and criteria for Evaluation of specific post-resection complications

Keywords: liver resections, complications after liver resections, hemorrhage

INTRODUCTION:

Prerequisites for the rapid development of liver resection surgery are the established anatomical knowledge of segmental hepatic anatomy, the improvement of techniques for parenchymal dissection and definitive hemo- and biliostasis, the improvement of hepatoprotection methods and means, the development of anesthesia and resuscitation care for operated patients.

OBJECTIVE:

Determination of a possible prognostic role of the type of liver resection (anatomic or atypical) for the risk of occurrence, frequency and severity of postoperative specific complications- hemorrhage.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

For the period from January, 2007 - March, 2018 in Clinic of liver, biliary pancreatic and general surgery, Acibadem City Clinic Tokuda Hospital ,1021 interventions were performed on the liver:

Cases of intervention other than liver resection by definition were excluded ISGLS, "removal of part of the liver parenchyma due to involvement by a disease process or traumatic injury resulting in devitalization of the parenchyma".

Thus, the study did not find the cases of:

- hepatotomy;
- cystotomies and cyst resections, practically without removal of functioning or pathologically altered liver parenchyma;
- liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors. liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors;
- interruption of trunk branches of the hepatic artery and/or portal vein with the aim of hypoperfusion of a given area (segments, lobe);
- suture of the liver in trauma;

Thus, a total of 852 cases of liver resections were included in the series

RESULTS:

Postresection hemorrhage is the most common life-threatening complication necessitating reoperations after liver resections, especially if they are large volume or part of a multivisceral resection. Among our patients, we reported a total of 10 hemorrhages, with a greater frequency occurring in Anatomic vs. Atypical liver resections and as a stand-alone procedure (2.6% vs. 0.5%, respectively), and as part of a multivisceral resection (2.6% vs. 0.7%, respectively) . Despite the stark difference in percentage terms, both lacked statistical significance. /Table 1/

Table 1.

Incidence of postoperative hemorrhage after liver resection

Another operation	Hemorrhage	Statistics	Anatomic resection	Atypical resection	total	P
no	no	N	113	218	331	0,302
		%	97,4%	99,5%	98,8%	
	yes	N	3	1	4	
		%	2,6%	,5%	1,2%	
yes	no	N	111	401	512	0,124
		%	97,4%	99,3%	98,8%	
	yes	N	3	3	6	
		%	2,6%	,7%	1,2%	

According to the International Study Group of Liver Surgery (ISGLS) criteria, two of the hemorrhages were Grade A (transfusion substituted up to 2 Er-mass units), another two were Grade B (requiring transfusion of more than 2 Er-mass units), and six were Grade C, requiring reoperations. We established the following facts: [1,2,3,4,5,6,]

1: postoperative hemorrhages appeared already in the first 24 hours after the end of the operation, and we had no cases of "late" hemorrhages - after the 72nd hour. Grade C bleeding had a different rate, and only in one case did we report a shock index >1. Bleeding from the resection surface was detected during the reoperation.

2: There were no patients with postoperative hemorrhage in the early postoperative period attributable to disorders of hemostasis, mainly thrombocytopenia and/or coagulopathy.

3: We reported five patients with the development of acute liver failure as a cause of fatal outcome in the early postoperative period. In four of them, we found post-resection hemorrhage, and in two it was Grade C.

A number of questions remain debatable and do not have unequivocal answers about the advantages and disadvantages of: [7-14]

- one or another method by which the liver parenchyma involved in the disease process will be removed - i.e. method of parenchymal dissection;

- for the application of clamping techniques in order to reduce intraoperative blood loss - type and characteristics of clamping;

- for the volume of the removed part of the liver

DISCUSSION:

The surgical technique itself must achieve:

- meticulous hemostasis of the resection surface

- minimized intraoperative blood loss, for which a clamping method can also be used

There is no universal method of liver resection.

Anatomic liver resection has a higher risk of acute liver failure in the early postoperative period due to loss of healthy, functioning liver parenchyma. But the majority of authors prove that the risks of hemorrhage are greater in atypical resection due to differences in the removed part of the segmental hepatic anatomy.

CONCLUSION:

Liver resection surgery should be performed in centers with sufficient experience in this field, working according to established standards and algorithms. Postresection hemorrhages are more common after Anatomic versus Atypical liver resections.

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